

the characters studied was considerably high and indicated the possibility of exploiting hybrid vigor for these traits. Among these hybrids, cross ADT41/ IR50 showed desirable heterobeltiosis for seven out of the nine

characters studied. The heterobeltiosis for this hybrid for kernel length was 1.23; kernel breadth, 5.70; kernel length-breadth ratio, 7.13; kernel length after cooking, -13.90; linear elongation, 8.70; elongation index, 22.97; amylose

content, 13.6; and protein per grain, 2.44. Duasan/ADT39 was promising for kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, and elongation index. ■

Variability and heritability estimates of yield and yield components in some Nigerian lowland rice genotypes

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The essential aspects of most, if not all, breeding programs can be divided into three stages: assembly or creation of a pool of variable germplasm, selection of superior individuals from the pool, and use of selected material for creating new populations to be employed as either potential commercial varieties or the base for a new cycle of selection. Estimates of genetic variance and

heritabilities can be of value in all three stages.

We studied 10 early-duration and 12 medium-duration rice genotypes during the 1994-95 cropping season (Jul-Nov) at the University Experimental Research Station (UERS) to select promising genotypes. The experiment was laid out using a randomized complete block design with 4- × 3-m plots and three replicates for the medium-duration genotypes and four for the early-duration genotypes.

Observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants per replication. Mean (X), standard deviation (SD), phenotypic coefficient of variability (PCV) and genotypic

coefficient of variability (GCV), broad-sense heritability (h^2), and genetic advance as percentage of mean (GA%) were calculated for 12 traits (see table).

Considerable differences were observed for all the traits in both medium- and early-duration rice genotypes, indicating wide variability and room for improvement through selection. The PCV was generally higher than the GCV in both early- and medium-duration genotypes. The differences were low for days to 50% heading, however, and plant height in the medium-duration rice group and panicle weight, panicle length, and seed weight panicle⁻¹ in the early-duration group.

A moderate amount of variability (10-20%) was observed for days to 50% heading, plant height, panicles m⁻², panicle weight, number of seeds panicle⁻¹, and 1000-seed weight in the medium-duration category, whereas in the early-duration category plant height, tillers m⁻², panicles m⁻², branches m⁻², seed weight panicle⁻¹, and 1000-seed weight showed a moderate amount of variability.

The medium-duration rice genotypes had very low GCV for panicle length and branches panicle⁻¹, whereas the early- duration rice had very low GCV for days to 50% heading and panicle length. High h^2 as well as high GA%, for the medium- duration group was observed for days to 50% heading, plant height, 1000-seed weight, and tillers m⁻². Dry biological yield and seed yield had high GA% while in the early-duration genotypes, seed weight panicle⁻¹, dry biological yield, and seed yield had high h^2 and GA%. High h^2 coupled with high GA% indicates a predominance of additive gene effects. ■

Genetic parameters for 12 traits in selected lowland rice genotypes. University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Nigeria, 1994-95.

Trait	Mean (X)	Standard deviation	Genotypic coefficient of variation	Phenotypic coefficient of variation	Broad sense heritability (h^2)	Genetic advance as % of mean
<i>Medium duration</i>						
50% heading (d)	87.5	10.80	70.64	10.06	91.18	18.92
Plant height (cm)	78.8	8.15	65.68	11.91	74.64	18.33
Tillers m ⁻² (no.)	207.7	28.00	1376.46	24.77	52.00	26.57
Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	188.3	33.80	322.02	14.73	42.00	12.76
Panicle length (cm)	24.5	1.04	1.24	6.94	43.00	6.16
Branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	10.4	1.04	0.24	7.81	36.00	5.80
Panicle weight (g)	4.0	0.50	0.17	16.77	37.78	13.07
Seeds panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	142.2	19.30	127.27	17.13	21.00	7.42
Seed weight panicle ⁻¹ (g)	3.43	0.76	0.44	30.58	40.00	13.30
1000 weight (g)	25.8	2.85	9.95	13.35	83.00	22.87
Dry biomass yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.21	0.97	2.46	43.05	49.00	43.52
Seed yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.85	0.96	0.76	37.00	37.00	28.32
<i>Early duration</i>						
50% heading (d)	79.60	4.03	5.21	5.88	78.50	9.58
Plant height (cm)	73.40	6.22	8.25	10.68	59.61	13.11
Tillers m ⁻² (no.)	205.88	39.20	12.64	18.96	44.43	17.36
Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	173.80	25.55	10.53	19.13	30.31	11.94
Panicle length (cm)	23.79	1.10	3.12	8.00	15.19	2.50
Branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	9.36	1.18	12.80	15.46	68.50	21.82
Panicle weight (g)	3.10	0.59	15.04	43.49	11.97	10.72
Seeds panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	127.40	17.26	10.95	21.61	25.68	11.43
Seed weight panicle ⁻¹ (g)	2.89	0.61	19.11	30.62	38.95	24.57
1000 seed weight (g)	25.69	2.30	8.75	10.76	66.16	14.66
Dry biomass yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.00	0.78	18.33	24.97	53.89	27.71
Seed yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.00	0.78	30.14	39.69	57.67	47.15